

ASSESSING THERMOGRAPHY AS AN IN-LINE QUALITY ASSURANCE METHOD FOR THERMOPLASTIC AUTOMATED FIBER PLACEMENT STRUCTURES

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Figure 1. Robotic-guided AFPT tape laying head with mounted thermography camera

Figure 2. Process scheme of in-situ thermoplastic tape laying with thermographic quality assurance of the cooldown behavior of applied tapes

In-situ automated fiber placement (in-situ T-AFP) is used for automated manufacturing of thermoplastic CFRP structures. A laser heats the individual tapes before layup and compaction, the consolidation roll provides cooling to achieve correct crystallization. An infrared-camera attached to the AFPT head monitors the residual heat for a process specific time, depending on field of view and layup speed. Differences in cooling rates can vary due to part design, tooling, inlays or flaws, thus enabling recognition of defects in the laminate.

Figure 3. Deposited tape monitored by thermographic camera during layup

- 3 tapes in one track
- Thermocouples as artificial defects
- KUKA fast send driver (FSD) triggers thermography camera
- FSD position and time for each picture are stored

Figure 4. Thermograms directly after deposition (1) and after cool down (2) with regions of interest (red = defect, blue = undisturbed laminate)

Position and time information is used to map the video stream and overlap the images regarding to the robot movement speed. This allows to track region of interests (ROI) that move through the image with the same velocity.

Figure 5. Cooling curves of defect (blue) and undisturbed (orange) laminate

The evaluation of two ROIs, one on the thermo coupling (defect) and the other on undisturbed tape shows great deviation in heat distribution. This effect can be used to determine defects induced during tape laying via inline thermography.

Thermography for in-line QA?

Cold Hot
Colormap Jet

Feasibility for flat parts was shown. Next developments will be done on curved parts. Since camera is fixed on the tape laying head, which is pivoting around the pressure roller, camera's field of view is changing due to curvature. Either optimized software (if applicable regarding the curvature) or additional actuators could be used to compensate the camera movement.